

MEDIA IN PUBLIC LIFE

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ABSTRACT

The fact that the Constitution provides a separate chapter for the media shows that their role in public life is great. The media is one of the most powerful tools of society, determining its development.

If we look at the functions of the media, they are: - the formation of appropriate opinions among the population; The media affects the human mind. Through this, the diversity of opinions enshrined in the constitution, freedom of speech, freedom of expression, which are the fundamental rights and freedoms of citizens, are realized. "Socio-political stability in the country depends sufficiently on the state of public opinion, and the media play an important role in its formation," the President said. - provides information about current events; - provides freedom of thought, speech, opinion; - represents the interests of various departments, political institutions; - protects the rights and freedoms of citizens; - Contributes to the deepening of democratic processes. "The most important condition for deepening the process of democratic renewal and ensuring the

freedoms of citizens in Uzbekistan is the implementation of specific measures to introduce democratic standards for the development of the media." Media evolves along with society. It can fully fulfill its function only with the support of the state and the existence of sufficient legal grounds. Therefore, the media, their activities are carried out in our country. not outside the reform. Their activities require constant improvement. In the late 1990s, it became necessary to reform the media. "Today, the radical reform of the media in Uzbekistan is becoming more and more obvious, because in the conditions of the ongoing changes, the pace of democratization of the political and economic life of the country, the activities of the media do not meet the requirements. "Much has been done to improve the work of the media. The issues of increasing the role of the media in society, further

liberalizing the press, television and radio, ensuring their independence and freedom in practice are five priorities for reform and renewal. In our life. The media occupy a worthy place in the life of society. . The media, in addition to promoting the policy of liberalizing reforms in the country, conveyed its essence to the population. Reforms and liberalization have a significant impact on their activities. In the "Concept for further deepening democratic reforms and the development of civil society in our country", put forward by the President, Chapter III. Strategic the objectives of this issue were defined as "Reforming the information sphere and ensuring freedom of speech." "Today we are talking about deepening the democratic process, increasing the political activity of the population, the practical participation of citizens in the political and public life of our country without ensuring freedom of information," he said. We are fine we understand that this goal cannot be achieved without turning it into a platform for free expression of our attitude and position in relation to current events. " ¹. Article 67 of the Constitution provides for freedom of the media and the rule of law, which means that the media must operate freely and in accordance with the law. As a result of the work carried out in our country to improve the activities of the media, a number of legal documents were adopted that guarantee their freedom, including: "On Copyright and Related Rights", April 1997, "On guarantees and freedom of information" , "On the Protection of Journalism", December 1997, "The Public. The Media Law is one of them. These laws are aimed at ensuring freedom of the media and improving their activities. Freedom of

the media depends primarily on the freedom of their employees, or rather journalists. There can be no freedom of the media without freedom of the journalist. Because the information is spread by journalists in the media. The Law on the Protection of Journalism clearly defines the rules governing broad institutional relationships related to the activities of journalists, as well as ensuring their freedom. It is not enough to have a law guaranteeing the freedom of a journalist; he must have sufficient knowledge and skills to use this freedom correctly and purposefully. Therefore, in our country, special attention is paid to training and retraining of journalists and media workers. Their training is based on international experience. Former educational institutions for journalists have been reorganized and equipped with modern equipment. Universities have faculties and courses for international journalists. In this regard, by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of February 26, 1999 "On improving the system of training and retraining of journalists", the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 2, 2005 held a two-year special course "Higher journalism". at the National University of Uzbekistan, the decision to open it played an important role. It was noted that the Constitution states that the media must act in accordance with the law. There are many specific laws governing media activities, some of which we have already mentioned. In addition, there are many other laws that regulate the activities of mass media and journalists. For example, the Law on Informatization, the Law on Advertising, the Law on the Protection of State Secrets and other laws. By the 20th anniversary of our

country, many new laws have been adopted concerning the activities of the media, or amendments have been made to existing laws. The concept was put forward by the President on November 12, 2010. initiates a new stage in the organization of the legal framework of the media. It says that the first law "On the transparency of public administration" should be adopted. This will allow citizens to more fully exercise their constitutional right to information. Secondly, there is a proposal to adopt a law "On Television and Radio Broadcasting" aimed at developing the television and radio

system, one of the most important sectors of information and communication. Further strengthening of the freedom and independence of third-party media is directly related to the strengthening of legal guarantees and mechanisms for reliable protection of copyright and intellectual property, the introduction of market mechanisms in the field of information. To solve this problem, it was proposed to adopt the laws "On the economic basis of the media", "On guarantees of state support for the media."

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